

1 **The range of Xist transcriptional targets in non-small cell lung cancer: SLAMF9.**

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6 We discovered aberrant activation of Xist in cancer, the non-coding RNA that silences duplicate X
7 chromosomes in females to execute dosage compensation, by studying whole transcription in
8 p53-sufficient and p53-deficient cancer cells (1). We next described high levels of Xist expression that
9 could be triggered by mutation or loss of either of two major tumor suppressors, p53 or Rb (1, 2). We
10 demonstrated a function for Xist in activation and repression of solid tumor gene expression, in humans
11 with breast cancer, driven by p53 loss, and demonstrated a role for the expression of these Xist-modulated
12 genes in subtype selection (instruction of tumor lineage) in breast cancer (3, 4). We also described the
13 existence of Xist ribonucleic protein (Xist RNP) complexes that putatively functioned to dynamically control
14 gene expression in transformed cells (5).

15 We describe here Xist control of transcriptional targets in the lung during transformation (6-9). We
16 demonstrate control of *SLAMF9* gene expression by Xist and a role for this gene expression control in
17 subtype selection in non-small cell lung cancer. Xist activation is likely a widespread and relatively
18 common biological phenomena during solid tumor development and disease progression driven by loss of
19 tumor suppressor (p53/Rb) function. Xist influences subtype selection in non-small cell lung cancer by
20 modulating expression of a wide range of transcriptional targets.
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Results

Here we used cells engineered to contain an Xist transgene, Xist-positive (Xist+) human embryonic stem cell clones, and epithelial cells of the lung that exhibit Xist activation following genetic depletion of p53 (6-8) to demonstrate Xist functions in control of gene expression across the transcriptome and in tumor lineage specification (subtype selection) in lung cancer (9).

Figure 1: Expression of SLAMF9 defines the squamous subtype in non-small cell lung cancer.

GSE74706

n=10 adenocarcinoma

n=8 squamous cell carcinoma

Probe ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	% DE
A_23_P96833	5.87E-03	-3.1024501	-2.41989	-7.38E-01	SLAMF9	1758/34183	94.9

In patients with non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC), expression of endothelial cell adhesion molecule *SLAMF9* defined the subtype (Figure 1). We discovered subtype-biased expression of *SLAMF9* by measuring and comparing total transcription between adeno and squamous subtypes of the most prevalent solid tumor type affecting humans, NSCLC.

Figure 2: In human bronchial epithelial cells, SLAMF9 perturbation is concomitant with Xist activation resulting from p53 depletion by shRNA.

GSE272045

n=1 bronchial epithelial cells (HBEC)

n=2 HBEC with p53 depletion (*n*=1 p53 shRNA HBEC and *n*=1 p53 shRNA HBEC with mutant KRas)

Probe ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	% DE
1553770_a_at	0.246481	-1.37	-4.59	-2.29	SLAMF9	9516/54675	82.6

Transient depletion of p53 which resulted in Xist activation was associated with significant modulation of *SLAMF9* expression when studying p53 depletion in cells of the lung *in vitro* (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Transgenic insertion of a gene encoding Xist in human cells results in modulation of SLAMF9 gene expression.

GSE68109

n=1 HT1080 fibrosarcoma cell line; vector control (5 day DOX induction)

n=2 HT1080 fibrosarcoma cell line with 1p Xist integration (5 day DOX induction)

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
89886	2.57E-01	1.791	1.13	2.0289883	18.33	SLAMF9	1905/18311	89.6

1 In human cells engineered to contain an Xist transgene, forced Xist expression resulted in
2 significant repression of SLAMF9 (Figure 3).

3 **Discussion**

4 We provided evidence here describing control of expression of the SLAMF9 gene by the
5 non-coding RNA Xist and a role for Xist-driven gene expression control in lineage determination at the
6 clonal level during solid tumorigenesis in humans with non-small cell lung cancer. Like in humans with
7 breast cancer, Xist activation that occurs very early is important for subtype selection and imparts a lasting
8 influence on tumor gene expression at clinical presentation. We are currently studying the molecular
9 mechanisms governing transcriptional induction of Xist; repair of the DNA during replication and damage
10 are candidate pathways that regulate Xist activation (11-13).

Methods

We used datasets GSE68109, GSE87231, GSE272045 and GSE74706 and for this quantitative differential gene expression study of Xist expression in the primary tumors of humans with non-small cell lung cancer, of the adeno and squamous types.

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